

OPERATIONAL-TACTICAL COMBINATIONS IN THE CRIMINALISTICS INVESTIGATION OF BRIBERY

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Abstract

Corruption manifests in numerous forms and guises; a paradigmatic form of corruption is bribery, which under Macedonian criminal law is criminalized by two offences contained in Chapter 30 of the Criminal Code of the Republic of North Macedonia: Receiving a Bribe (Article 357) and Giving a Bribe (Article 358). (Official Gazette of the Republic of North Macedonia, no. 37/96 ... 248/18.) The subject of this study comprises the operational-tactical combinations employed in the criminal investigation of these offences with the aim of detecting, clarifying and securing evidence. This category of corrupt conduct requires investigative responses that are themselves specific: planned combinations of operational-tactical measures, investigative acts and special investigative techniques, selected and implemented according to the concrete criminal situation. Methodologically, the paper applies the normative method in order to examine the statutory regulation of these offences and employs statistical and comparative methods to obtain data on the volume, structure and dynamics of these crimes for the period 2020–2024. It further analyses the volume, structure and dynamics of reported, indicted and convicted offenders, and examines the collected and systematized data to derive informed conclusions about the state of affairs in the Republic of North Macedonia. Finally, the study undertakes a review and analysis of legally prescribed measures and actions and their operational-tactical combination.

Keywords: corruption; receiving a bribe; giving a bribe; operational combinations; criminal investigation.

INTRODUCTION

In an organized society, nothing poses a greater threat to the functioning of public services and the performance of public duties than the susceptibility to bribery—the corruption of those who hold such positions. At the same time, corruption represents an attack on the freedoms and rights of citizens, as it undermines one of the fundamental principles of the rule of law: the equality of all citizens before the law. Moreover, corrupt public officials perform their duties inefficiently, subordinating the public interest to private (self-serving) gain. Corruption becomes a mode of behaviour, a form of communication, a method of negotiation, and a means of escape from “hopeless” situations; as the old saying goes, “*money opens iron gates*”. And money is corruption itself: both the means and the medium of communication, negotiation, and the completion

of tasks. Yet can everyone afford to pay? We are speaking of a state governed by rule of law, where both the rich and the poor live. For the wealthy, things come easily; for the poor, it is much more difficult (Nikoloska, 2013).

Corruption is a form of behaviour that deviates from formal rules in the exercise of public duties, undertaken for the purpose of achieving personal gain or violating the rules governing the conduct of individuals who are elected, appointed, or employed in positions involving the performance of public office, activity, or profession. According to Tanzi (1998), corruption represents the deliberate disregard of official distance, aimed at obtaining certain benefits for oneself or for closely related persons. In the pre-modern world, corruption was described as humanity's original sin—that is, as a manifestation of sinful human behaviour (Knights, 2016).

Corruption is defined as the offering, receiving, or demanding of certain benefits with the intent to influence social actions. Aristotle, Machiavelli, and Montesquieu identified corruption as a sign of the erosion of a society's moral values. They regarded it as an immoral and harmful phenomenon, emphasizing that holders of public office must serve the common good rather than their own private interests. With the development of the modern state, corruption can no longer be viewed merely as a morally harmful phenomenon, but also as a cause of state deterioration. (Labovic, 2024) The most significant forms of corruption include the giving and receiving of bribes and nepotism, the abuse of one's position for personal purposes. Declared social values—particularly the pursuit of success at any cost—appear to encourage the spread of corrupt practices. Individual corruption refers to the actions of a single person within a corrupt exchange. This form of activity is discreet, involving only two participants. Such acts are characterized by the culpability of both parties in the giving and receiving of bribes or gifts. This type of corruption is the most prevalent among all forms. Corruption between public officials and private individuals is especially widespread. The simplest form in this sphere is the bribery of public officials. When such practices become common within an institution, the integrity of that institution is called into question. If such practices are characteristic of several institutions, one can speak of an endemic phenomenon of corruption within state institutions (Dobovšek & Meško, 2009).

If a briber resolves a problem in this manner and has no other means of doing so, then, according to the traditional norms of the community in which he lives, he is not subject to moral condemnation (Antonić, 2001: 26). In other words, within popular tradition, bribery is tacitly tolerated and even met with a degree of understanding. Based on centuries of collective experience, bribery has become a kind of folkloric and everyday phenomenon. It is often rationalized by the attitude: *"Everyone does it"* (Antonić, 2001: 27). Over time, this has developed into a habitual practice that facilitates the completion of various affairs and has persisted in popular experience as a sort of maxim: *"Grease the wheels if you want the job done faster"*. Today, it is still common to hear expressions such as: *"Get this thing done for me, and I'll reward you"* (Antonić, 2001). Of course, this "reward" does not represent honour in its original sense, but rather a euphemism—a "more refined" expression—for a bribe, that is, an act of corruption.

As a traditional form of corruption, bribery encompasses both the giving and receiving of illicit benefits. Giving a bribe (or offering a bribe) involves providing money or other valuables in the form of a gift, typically to unlawfully secure the execution of an action, to obtain preferential treatment (jumping the queue), or to gain certain privileges. The act of giving a bribe or engaging in bribery constitutes a process whereby material, financial, or other services are offered to those upon whom the provision of specific

services or the granting of favourable treatment depends—individuals who are legally obligated to perform such duties. Bribery is considered the most widespread form of corruption, particularly in the context of administrative corruption, which entails the subordination of public interest to personal gain (Joković Pantelić, 2024). It generates a dual benefit: for the briber, who unlawfully secures a right or privilege, and for the bribee, who unlawfully derives personal gain at the expense of public interest and the office or service they are legally entrusted to uphold. In this context, both parties are perpetrators of a criminal offence. Bribery-related crime is closely linked to circumstances associated with public authority, particularly the discretionary powers of the bribe recipient, while the briber seeks to obtain certain advantages, services, or even facilitate the commission of other criminal acts—such as document forgery—as a direct result of the bribe.

Bribery constitutes a complex criminal situation, regardless of whether it involves an isolated criminal case or an organized criminal scheme, because the participants (the perpetrator and the victim) each have their own criminal interests. The individual offering the bribe does so to achieve a particular objective—obtaining employment, a service, a privileged status—or may be compelled to offer a bribe to secure such outcomes, as demanded by the other party, the bribe recipient. Both parties have vested interests, as the acceptance of a bribe can be carried out by individuals holding the status of public officials, persons in positions of responsibility, or individuals performing work of public interest, a status defined under Article 122 of the Criminal Code of the Republic of North Macedonia (Official Gazette of the RM, no. 37/96 ... 248/18). Moreover, a bribe can be offered by any person, either a natural person or a legal entity (through a responsible person or other employee acting on behalf of and for the account of the legal entity). In most cases, bribery is not reported, and this form of crime thus falls within the so-called “dark figure” of criminality.

It is a practice of legal incrimination for “receiving” and “giving” a bribe. In this case, there is an intertwining of the role of the victim and that of the perpetrator, and it is questionable whether someone would report these criminal acts in practice (Dobovšek & Mesko, 2009).

Criminal-investigative inquiry into bribery is a complex process of detection, elucidation, and proof, and it also serves as a preventive function. It is held that every well-processed case constitutes effective prevention for prospective offenders who may be contemplating this type of crime.

The conduct of a criminal-investigative inquiry depends on the complexity of the criminal situation, the initial findings, and their operational verification. Whether the matter concerns an isolated incident or organized criminal activity, investigations into this type of offending always involve the planning and execution of operational–tactical combinations of lawful measures and actions aimed at full detection, clarification, and evidential securing. Because this is a specific form of corrupt behaviour the operational–tactical combinations are planned and implemented with the objective of apprehending perpetrators *in flagrante*. With careful operational planning, detection, clarification, and the securing of robust evidence necessary for the subsequent course of criminal proceedings can be achieved simultaneously.

In complex criminal situations, the planning and employment of covert measures require a longer time horizon, while execution is governed by precisely determined times and locations for carrying out the lawful measures and actions.

2. CRIMINAL-LEGAL CHARACTERISTICS OF BRIBERY IN THE REPUBLIC OF NORTH MACEDONIA

Under Macedonian criminal law, Chapter 30 of the Criminal Code (Criminal offences Against Official Duty) (Official Gazette of the RM, nos. 37/96...248/18) criminalizes two offences involving elements of bribery. These offences share similar criminal-investigative characteristics and are considered either connected or sequential. In order for a bribe to be received, there must be a party willing to give or actively offering the bribe.

2.1. Receiving a Bribe – Article 357

Receiving a Bribe, or, as it is commonly referred to in all international anti-corruption instruments, passive bribery, is one of the forms of corruption. The perpetrators of this criminal offence are public or responsible officials, and a key element of the offence is that the bribe is offered or received in connection with the performance of official duties—specifically, in the execution of certain official acts within the perpetrator's competence. According to Article 357 of the Criminal Code, receiving a bribe constitutes criminal behaviour by a public official who, directly or indirectly, solicits or accepts a gift or other benefit, or receives a promise of a gift or benefit, for themselves or another, in order to perform an official act that they should not perform or to refrain from performing an official act that they are obligated to execute. It also includes a public official who, directly or indirectly, solicits or accepts a gift or other benefit, or receives a promise of a gift or benefit, to perform an official act that they are required to execute or to refrain from performing an official act that they should not perform. Furthermore, the offence encompasses cases where, after performing or failing to perform an official act as described above, the official solicits, accepts, or agrees to accept a gift or other benefit. If the offence results in the acquisition of substantial or significant material gain, higher penalties are prescribed. The same penalties apply to responsible people, individuals performing tasks of public interest, as well as foreign officials. Any gift or material benefit received shall be confiscated. (Criminal Code of the RM, Official Gazette no. 37/96...248/18)

Primarily, by criminalizing these actions, the legislator aimed to protect the proper functioning of public services. The purpose of this criminalization is to prevent the unlawful acquisition of material gain, and, in essence, the offence is considered a criminal act against property.

As a rule, the acceptance of a bribe is accompanied by the performance of unlawful official acts. In cases where the public official does not undertake any official action, the mere acceptance of a bribe compromises the lawful execution of their duties. The bribe obliges the official to act in an impermissible manner while performing their duties, and, in addition to this improper conduct, a key element is the material gain and the abuse of official position. (Labovic, 2024) In terms of execution, accepting a bribe constitutes one form of abuse of official authority. Objectively, this criminal offence also constitutes a violation of the authority of the office and the public's trust in the lawful conduct of officials. In carrying out their official duties, public officials must be guided by the interests of the office rather than by personal gain (Vitlarov, 2006). Receiving a bribe is considered a particularly serious criminal offence because it represents a breach of the rules governing official conduct and undermines the reputation of both the officials and the office itself. Moreover, such behaviour may create habits in officials, leading them to

solicit and accept bribes or rewards in the future. For public and responsible officials, bribery can become normalized behaviour, where decisions are guided by the size of the bribe rather than by the rules of conduct imposed by their official position, making their actions dependent on who offers a bribe and how much it is worth.

The acceptance of a bribe can take the form of **active acceptance** (directly or indirectly through intermediaries), which involves soliciting a bribe or creating a situation in which a certain action of the perpetrator must be paid for. **Passive bribery**, on the other hand, occurs when the bribe is not solicited but is received “for a job well done”—either directly or indirectly—for failing to perform a certain duty that the official is obligated or required to carry out in the course of their official responsibilities (Nikoloska, 2013).

2.2. Giving a Bribe – Article 358

Giving a bribe (active bribery) is intrinsically linked to passive bribery. While receiving a bribe implies consent or willingness to be corrupted, giving a bribe constitutes active corruption, involving the inducement or encouragement of a public official, responsible person, foreign official, individual performing work of public interest, or foreign public official, to engage in unlawful conduct. In this respect, both parties, the briber and the bribee—are involved. However, this connection does not necessarily always apply, as giving a bribe can also constitute an independent offence in cases where the perpetrator offers a bribe without the official or other legally designated person intending to accept it. If the bribe is not accepted and the incident is reported, the liability for the criminal offence of giving bribe rests solely with the briber (Nikoloska, 2013).

In the criminal offence of giving a bribe, the perpetrator is any person who directly or indirectly gives, promises, or offers a gift or other benefit to a public official for themselves or another, in order to induce the official to perform an act that they should not perform, or to refrain from performing an act that they are obligated to execute, as well as any person who mediates in this process. The offence also covers those who directly or indirectly give, promise, or offer a gift or other benefit to a public official for themselves or another, to induce the official to perform an act they are required to execute or to refrain from performing an act they should not perform, including intermediaries. A court may exempt from punishment a perpetrator who gave or promised a bribe at the request of a public official and reported it before it was discovered that the offence had occurred. These provisions also apply when a bribe is given or promised to a responsible person, a responsible person in a foreign legal entity, a person performing work of public interest, or a foreign public official in connection with receiving a bribe. Criminal liability is also prescribed if the bribe is given by a legal entity. Any gift or material benefit provided shall be confiscated.

In cases where a bribe is given to induce a public official or another person to act in accordance with the law, that person is technically performing a lawful act. However, they violate the fundamental principle of equality of citizens before the law by granting certain advantages or benefits to the briber, or by exceeding the limits of their authority in the interest of the briber.

The connection between the briber and the bribee is established through the transmission of a message, the communication of conditions, the receipt of the gift from the giver, and its delivery to the recipient, among other actions. This encompasses all acts by which the giver’s intent is realized in any way, ensuring that the bribe or other benefit—or the promise thereof—reaches the recipient, namely the public official. In such cases, the intermediary acts as an instigator or facilitator of the bribery; however, the law

criminalizes these actions as execution of the offence, making the intermediary one of the perpetrators of this criminal act (Vitlarov, 2006).

3. VOLUME, STRUCTURE, AND DYNAMICS OF BRIBE PERPETRATORS IN THE REPUBLIC OF NORTH MACEDONIA FOR THE PERIOD 2020–2024

To gain insights into the state of bribery in our country, data were obtained and analysed from two sources: the Annual Reports of the Public Prosecutor’s Office and the Annual Reports of the Ministry of Interior.

Table 1. Data for the Investigated Period 2020–2024 (Annual Reports of the Public Prosecutor’s Office)

Year	Receiving a Bribe under Article 357			Giving a Bribe under Article 358			Total		
	Rep.	Ind.	Con.	Rep.	Ind.	Con.	Rep.	Ind.	Con
2020	4	5	6	0	0	0	4	5	6
2021	17	5	6	0	0	0	17	5	6
2022	23	9	2	5	5	6	28	14	8
2023	23	10	30	11	10	12	34	20	42
2024	40	13	8	19	7	5	59	20	13
Total	107	42	52	35	22	23	142	64	75

In Table 1, the data presented are obtained from the Annual Reports of the Public Prosecutor’s Office (jorm.gov.mk) for the two investigated criminal offences involving elements of bribery, covering the period 2020–2024. The data refers to reported, indicted, and convicted offenders, with the purpose of gaining insight into the effectiveness of criminal investigations and the securing of relevant and substantial evidence upon which the courts base their judgments. Specifically, during the investigated period, for the criminal offence “Receiving a Bribe”, a total of 107 offenders were reported, of whom 42 were indicted and 52 convicted. For the offence “Giving a Bribe”, a total of 35 offenders were reported, 22 indicted, and 23 convicted. In total, for both offences, 142 offenders were reported, 64 indicted, and 75 convicted. There is a higher number of reported, indicted, and convicted offenders for “Receiving a Bribe” compared to “Giving a Bribe”, which indicates that in most cases, victims report bribery or extortion attempts. Moreover, if a bribe is reported before the case is discovered, the briber is not held criminally liable. The conviction rate of 52.8% is higher than the indictment rate of 45.07%, which suggests two possible explanations: during the criminal proceedings, evidence was obtained against additional persons, or some of the proceedings have been ongoing over a longer period,

with indictments filed in previous years. Regarding the dynamics, the highest number of reported offenders for both offences—both collectively and individually—was recorded in 2024.

Table 2. Volume, Structure, and Dynamics of Detected Criminal offences and Reported Offenders for Bribery by the Ministry of Interior

Year	Receiving a Bribe		Giving a Bribe		Total	
	CO	P	CO	P	CO	P
2020	5	4	1	1	6	5
2021	3	5	4	4	7	9
2022	11	18	5	5	16	23
2023	11	12	11	12	22	24
2024	12	25	10	11	22	36
Total	42	64	31	33	73	97

In Table 2, the data are extracted from the Annual Reports of the Ministry of Interior for the investigated period 2020–2024 for the two examined criminal offences. The data refers to detected criminal offences and reported perpetrators. A total of 73 criminal offences were detected, of which 42 relate to receiving a bribe and 31 to giving a bribe. For these offences, a total of 97 perpetrators were reported, with 64 reported for receiving a bribe and 33 for giving a bribe. For the offence “Receiving a Bribe”, more criminal offences were detected and more perpetrators reported compared to “Giving a Bribe”, indicating that victims primarily report individuals with the status of “bribe recipients”, who are then processed through operational criminal-investigative procedures. According to the law, if the act of giving a bribe is reported before the bribe is delivered and there is cooperation with the police, the bribers are not held criminally liable. The fact that 73 criminal offences involved 97 perpetrators suggests that this type of crime is often committed by multiple individuals, in a grouped or organized manner.

According to the analysis of the Annual Reports of the Ministry of Interior, which also include data on the status of the perpetrators, the dominant perpetrators of receiving a bribe are police officers, (Labovic, 2024) particularly those working in traffic safety and the border police. Following them are customs officers. However, other public officials, responsible persons, and especially individuals performing work of public interest are also recipients of bribes. Regarding giving a bribe, again the most common recipients are police officers, with bribes given to avoid border checks, traffic fines, or controls. This type of crime is also present in areas such as urban planning, economic activities, and others. Reported perpetrators of receiving a bribe include suspects holding official positions in various ministries, state institutions, funds, and municipalities, as well as individuals performing work of public interest, such as doctors, pharmacists, and similar professions. (<https://portal.mdt.gov.mk/module-block-documents/76-document-mk.pdf>)

For the purpose of deeper scientific consideration of the practical consequences from the complexity of high-level institutional type of organized corruption see: Miodrag Labovic: Policing in Central and Eastern Europe – Social Control of Unconventional Deviance, Conference Proceedings, Social control of institutional organized crime. (Labovic, 2011)

Among the most notable cases in police practice for detecting high-level corruption involving the acceptance of bribes over an extended period and in an organized manner is the 2022 case in which an organized criminal group of 12 police officers at the Tabanovce Border Crossing was dismantled. Between September 2020 and onward, these officers acted jointly and in a coordinated manner, demanding and accepting bribes in the form of cash, gifts, and other benefits in exchange for overlooking detected irregularities. Some of the suspected police officers were charged not only with “Receiving a Bribe” under Article 357, but also with “Abuse of Official Position and Authority”, “Criminal Association”, and “Incitement”. In 2024, another notable case in the field of high-level corruption involved the tender process for the State Lottery of the Republic of North Macedonia, where, due to grounds for suspicion of “Receiving a Bribe” under Article 357, three individuals were reported. These included the Chairperson of the Management Board and the Chairperson and a member of the Public Call Commission. Also in 2024, an operational action targeting bribery among customs officers at the Novo Selo and Dojran border crossings resulted in the arrest of 13 customs officers for prolonged bribery. From May to October 2024, these officers repeatedly demanded and accepted bribes ranging from €20 to €100 to refrain from taking measures or actions related to the collection of customs duties.

OPERATIONAL–TACTICAL COMBINATIONS IN THE CRIMINALISTICS INVESTIGATION OF BRIBERY

The criminalistic investigation into bribery, as a specific form of corruption, is a process that spans information gathering to operational execution and is applied in complex criminal situations involving elements of bribery. Depending on the initial general information, operational checks are conducted to establish the level of suspicion—“grounds for suspicion”—in order to plan and implement lawful measures and actions. Each case requires a separate operational plan and individual operational–tactical combination, which most often culminates in an operational action: prior covert preparation and execution of a planned, secret operation that simultaneously involves multiple measures and actions to achieve detection, clarification, and the securing of substantial evidence. In this context, according to criminal-investigative characteristics, three typical situations most commonly occur: (1) a previously reported solicited bribe, where the “victim” is required to give a bribe, and the focus of the procedure is on the solicitation itself; (2) continuous bribery carried out by individual public officials, responsible persons, or persons performing work of public interest, where the corrupt acts are related to their ongoing official and professional duties; and (3) organized bribery, in which both parties—the givers and receivers of the bribe—have a shared interest, as often occurs in cases involving police and customs officers and omissions in supervision and control. In each of these scenarios, operational actions are tailored to the specific circumstances to enable effective detection, clarification, and secure evidence necessary for a successful judicial procedure (Nikoloska, 2025).

Criminalistic investigation inquiry into criminal situations is planned and executed on a case-by-case basis through the formulation of operational–tactical combinations of measures and actions — that is, operational–tactical, investigative measures and actions, and special investigative measures — with the aim of simultaneously detecting, elucidating, and securing evidence. This approach, known in criminology as apprehending perpetrators *in flagranti*, targets the moment of, or immediately after, the commission of the offence when the evidence (money, valuables) is still in their possession. The specific nature of these two corrupt offences makes such acts essential: without it, it is difficult to obtain robust and relevant evidence. For this reason, operational–tactical combinations are of crucial importance for the full elucidation of criminal situations and for securing the evidence necessary for a successful subsequent criminal procedure. The tactical method provides the most rational and effective manner of executing an operational–tactical measure, an investigative or judicial action — a choice made by the practitioner from the repertoire of criminological tactics that is most appropriate to the concrete operational–tactical or tactical–procedural situation. That discretion should be guided by the type of evidentiary material that can be obtained, following the principle of progressing from “weaker” to “stronger” evidence. From the perspective of covert criminological work, tactical combinations imply the application of measures and actions aimed at criminologically purposeful operations and at the preparation of operational actions founded on relevant data on which the criminal execution depends — a method especially pertinent in criminal situations such as illegal drug trafficking. These constitute fundamental police actions that should be employed in modern criminal investigation and should form the basis of all criminological planning, founded on criminological analysis and intelligence (Angeleski, 2018).

Operational-tactical combinations are planned and carried out in coordination with the competent public prosecutor’s office; measures are planned that can effectively execute the operation and fully shed light on the case by securing relevant evidence that links the perpetrator to the criminal offence. A tactical combination is a system of two or more interconnected measures and actions and multiple tactical methods for implementing them, adapted to the specific criminal situation. The tactical combination represents “the union of several tactical methods, multiple operational-tactical measures, investigative actions or special investigative measures, which may be mutually connected and undertaken according to a previously prepared plan” (Vodinielić, 1985). When conducting operational combinations, account is taken of the degree of organization of the criminal group, their *modus operandi*, any connections of individuals within the prosecuting authorities or their corrupt conduct; particular care must be taken with the covert planning of measures and actions in order to find and secure evidence of the offence and evidence that links the offence to the perpetrator and other persons involved in the criminal operation.

Tactical combinations from the perspective of covert criminalistic operations imply the application of measures and actions aimed at criminalistically purposeful work and the preparation of operational actions based on relevant data that determine the criminal execution, particularly in criminal situations involving illegal drug trafficking. These are fundamental police actions that should be employed in modern criminal investigations, and they should form the basis of any criminalistic planning, grounded in criminalistic analysis and intelligence (Angeleski, 2018).

The investigation of more complex criminal cases is carried out through operational actions; it involves planned and coordinated procedures with the implementation of scheduled measures and actions according to a pre-drawn plan

specifying the place and time for those measures and actions, as well as the human and technical resources. Operational-tactical actions are measures and activities undertaken within a defined time period, with predetermined objectives, and under full coordination and control from a single centre where all information and data from the measures and actions are collected. Although they may be conducted over an extended period, they culminate in the arrest of the perpetrators and their presentation before an investigating judge. Operational-tactical actions are given a designation — usually chosen by the operational officers or the investigative team — depending on the subject of the criminal investigation or the area of the perpetrators' criminal activity.

Most often, operational-tactical combinations in individual cases of accepting a bribe — that is, when victims report that a bribe has been solicited from them — involve cooperation with police officers by giving the officers “marked banknotes” (previously photocopied); in the past these were marked with chemical substances for that purpose. The time and place are determined precisely, of course in agreement with the “victim”, and then operational-tactical measures are applied: an ambush, covert tailing and observation. At the moment of execution the suspects are detained, the items — the bribe — are seized, searches are carried out and interviews conducted; all of this is directed from a single centre — the commander of the operation and the competent public prosecutor.

For complex criminal cases, elaborate operational-tactical combinations are developed, involving a complete and detailed action plan. Special investigative measures are applied — such as monitoring communications and deploying undercover police operatives — with the goal of executing the operation at the moment the suspects accept a bribe or when the bribe money is in their possession. During this process, suspects are detained, interviews are conducted, and simultaneously, inspections and searches are carried out in business premises, including review of business documents, seizure of camera recordings and computer data. Searches are also conducted in homes, other involved individuals are detained, and all measures and actions are documented in appropriate reports, which serve as evidence of the lawful execution of all measures and activities. Particular attention is given to evidence, which must be seized with confirmation of temporarily secured items and then delivered with proper documentation to the public prosecutor's office. Every well-executed criminal-legal event is the result of the efficiency of all individuals involved in the implementation of operational-tactical combinations and in the operation itself.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Bribery is a traditional form of corruption that manifests through the giving and receiving of bribes. In cases of receiving a bribe, the perpetrators are individuals with official status, whereas in cases of giving a bribe, the perpetrators can be private individuals or responsible persons within legal entities who give bribes on behalf of and for the account of the legal entities, most often in tender procedures.

Based on investigative results, receiving a bribe is a criminal offence committed more frequently than giving a bribe. This is due to the fact that victims report instances of bribery; if they report the offence, they are not criminally liable.

In our country, bribery is most commonly observed among police officers, particularly in the traffic and border police, as well as among customs officials. It is usually carried out in an organized manner for smaller amounts but continuously over an extended period.

High-value bribes are most often associated with tenders, which is understandable given the exceptionally large sums involved.

Bribery as an individual case occurs among persons performing public interest duties. These involve smaller or occasionally larger amounts, and this type of corruption undermines public trust in institutions, especially in healthcare institutions, funds, or state agencies.

Good planning and execution of operational-tactical combinations through operational actions are effective, and securing relevant evidence enables further efficiency in criminal proceedings.

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